

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

A high-yielding, early-maturing variety for the rainfed uplands of Orissa

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Subhadra (DR92), a pedigree selection from TNI/SR26R from the Bhubaneswar Dry land Agriculture Research Centre, has been released by the Orissa State Variety Release Committee for general cultivation in rainfed uplands throughout the state.

The short-statured variety has an average plant height of 70 cm, moderate tillering ability, coarse (medium bold) grains, about 40,000 grains/kg, and good cooking quality. Maturity is about 90 d. The variety is

drought tolerant and responds well to fertilizers. Yields are stable, with little insect and disease problems.

As a direct seeded kharif crop, Subhadra yielded consistently higher than Bala, Annapurna, and other standard high-yielding varieties in multilocal trials in rainfed uplands (Table 1).

In 1976–78 tests at 4 dryland research centers outside Orissa, Subhadra was the highest yielder at Dehradun (4.1 t/ha) and Rewa (3.2 t/ha); its performance was commendable at Ranchi (2.5 t/ha) and Varanasi (2.1 t/ha). In the northeastern hill states — Meghalaya, Manipur, and Sikkim (500–1,000 m altitude) — it was found suitable for direct seeding and transplanting (Table 2). It was tolerant of blast disease and matured in about 140–145 d. □

Table 1. Grain yield of Subhadra in kharif multilocal tests (1973–79), Orissa, India.

Location	Yield (t/ha)			Increase (%)
	Years (no.)	Subhadra	Bala (check)	
Bhubaneswar	5	2.0	1.6	25
Chiplima	3	2.0	1.2	61
Joshipur	3	2.4	2.0	20
Berhampur	1	3.5	3.2	9
Overall average		2.4	2.0	20

Table 2. Grain yield of Subhadra in the northeastern hill regions, India.

Location	Yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)
	Subhadra	Local check	
Meghalaya	2.6	2.3	14
Manipur	5.0	3.2	55
Sikkim	2.8	1.6	70

TPS1a short-duration red rice in Tamil Nadu

S. Kalaimani, O. Ramanathapillai, S. Palanisamy, G. Radhakumar, and A. Idhyarajan, Paddy Experiment Substation (PES), Thirupathisaram 629901, Tamil Nadu, India

A promising short-duration red rice culture TP1334-1 to replace the local variety Kattisamba in Kanyakumari District performed well in 1980–84 yield trials and in the 1983–84 Adaptive Research Trials in farmers' fields. It was released by the state

varietal release committee in 1985 as TPS1. This is the first variety released from the Thirupathisaram PES, Tamil Nadu.

TPS1, a derivative of IR8/ Kattisamba, is semitall (110 cm), matures in 110-115 d, and has higher

yield potential than local Kattisamba. It is medium tillering with light green foliage and good panicle exertion. Panicles are long and compact.

Average grain yields of 5.0 t/ha, 17.8% more than those of Kattisamba, have been recorded. Production

potential is 7.8 t/ha. Average straw yield is 9.2 t/ha. The grain is short bold with a red kernel closely resembling that of Kattisamba. It possesses good cooking quality.

TPS1 has field tolerance for stem borer. □

Rice variety resistant to gall midge (GM) and bacterial blight (BB) released in Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

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Usha, a semidwarf high yielding rice variety with resistance to GM and BB, has been released for general cultivation in MP. Usha is derived from IR22/W1263. It resembles IR22 in plant type. IR22 is susceptible to GM and BB but Usha and W1263 are

Table 1. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of TN1 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction			
	F ₁	F ₂		
		Resist	ant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)
TN1/Usha	Resistant	671	245	1:40
TN1/W1263	Resistant	287	113	2.08

Table 2. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of IR22 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction		
	F ₁	F ₂	
		Resistant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)
IR22/Usha	Resistant	856	0
IR22/W1263	Resistant	406	0

resistant at Raipur, MP. A single dominant gene *GMI* conferred Usha's resistance to the GM biotype.

A single dominant gene also conferred resistance to BB (Table 1). Usha and W1263 have the same allelic gene *Xa-4* as IR22 has (Table 2).

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Influence of vegetative growth duration on grain grade

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The vegetative growth (VG) period of BPI-76, a photoperiod-sensitive cultivar, was altered to 45, 65, 85, and 105 d by manipulating photoperiod. Plants were grown in 4-liter plastic pots in the glasshouse. Each pot contained 3.5 kg soil fertilized with 4 g ammonium sulfate, 2 g solophos, and 2 g muriate of potash. Five plants per pot were grown under 24-h photoperiod. Sowings were staggered.

Plants were transferred to 10-h photoperiod so that climatic conditions during reproductive and ripening phases were similar. Grain grade was determined by the specific gravity method.

Grain yield was higher with 45 and 65 d VG (see table) and gradually

Influence of vegetative growth duration on number of different grades of grain per hill.^a IIRRI, 1986.

Parameter	Vegetative growth duration			
	45 d	65 d	85 d	105 d
Grain yield/hill (g)	6.8 a	6.2 a	5.4 b	4.4 c
Panicles/hill	3.8 a	3.1 b	2.7 c	3.1 d
Total spikelets	459 a	429 ab	381 bc	336 c
Empty spikelets	54 a	72 a	70 a	74 a
	(11)	(16)	(18)	(22)
Poor grains ^b	46 a	44 a	34 a	24 a
	(8)	(10)	(9)	(7)
Average ^b	157 a	115 a	42 b	38 b
	(28)	(32)	(10)	(11)
Good ^b	200 a	198 a	233 a	193 a
	(49)	(41)	(66)	(59)
High density grains ^b	1.5 a	1.0 a	2.2 a	0.7 a
	(4)	(2)	(5)	(3)
Total grains	405 a	358 b	311 c	262 d
	(89)	(84)	(83)	(78)

^aFigures in parentheses are percent of respective grades of total spikelets. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bPoor grains = collected from 1.0-1.06 specific gravity; average grains, 1.08-1.12 specific gravity; good grains, 1.14 to 1.10 specific gravity; and high density grains, 1.20 specific gravity.

decreased with increased growth duration. The higher grain yield at 45 and 65 d was due mainly to high panicle numbers, fertility percentage, and total grain numbers per hill.

High density (HD) grain yield (grains which submerge at 1.20 sp gr) was not related to VG duration. BPI-76 produced hardly any HD grains; production of HD grain did not differ